

THE EFFECT OF INTERNET GAMES ON YOUTH PSYCHOLOGY AND WORKING WITH YOUTH ADDICTED TO GAMES

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Abstract. *This article talks about the impact of the internet, internet games, which have entered our lives and is spreading widely among all layers of our society, on our lifestyle today and its negative impact on the psyche of young people. In addition, the article analyzes the rules of rational use of the Internet, the aspects that should be paid attention to in order not to become addicted to virtual games, and the opinions of advanced foreign and Uzbek scientists on this topic are presented.*

Keywords: *internet, internet games, youth, education, upbringing, social networks, disease, dependence, existence, mass culture, strategy, auction, television, society.*

INTRODUCTION. We live in such a time that we cannot spend a single day without the Internet. If we don't enter for a day, it's like we've lost something. Someone to get news, someone to share information, someone to learn, someone to play games, someone to satisfy their lust, someone just to pass the time from idleness, someone to watch movies, someone to download the necessary programs, someone to gain wealth, someone uses the internet to cheat someone, someone to develop their business, someone to buy something.

Ehh, the list could go on and on. Did you find yourself among these? What do you use the internet for? Are you clear on your goals? Does your goal contribute to the benefit of yourself or your family, to the development of society, to the development of our country? Can you always walk steadily without deviating from this goal? Aren't you distracted by the charming conspiracies of the Internet? Are you adequately protected against invisible attacks in it? Do you always feel that God is witnessing everything you do and that angels are recording your actions? Of course, the Internet serves to make our distance close, our burden light, our work easier. In this article, we will not dwell on the positive aspects of the Internet. Along with many positive aspects, there are aspects that we all need to be aware of, that require vigilance when using the Internet.

When talking about Internet attacks, first of all, it is necessary to remember ideological, ideological, news, psychological, political, military, economic attacks. Because the 21st century is the age of information. A single piece of information (false, destructive or misleading) can cause conflicts, disagreements, and even bloody wars within an entire country or between peoples, nations, people, or between countries and continents.

In the first place, it is appropriate to talk about attacks of religious mischief. In this place, issues such as apostasy, irreligiousness, preaching to other religions, religious extremism and incitement to terrorism can be cited. This attack is one of the most terrible attacks of today, and its consequences are not necessary to be written, because it is impossible not to remember the atrocities that are causing the death of people in some part of the world every day.

In addition, there are attacks on promiscuity, violence, carelessness, laziness and other negative aspects aimed at disrupting the education of young people. These attacks also lead to the

corruption of the growing young generation, and as a result, the destruction of the whole people, nation, and society, the spread of various corruptions, conspiracies, thefts, robberies, adultery, and prostitution.

Economic attacks are next. In this case, it will be possible to present attacks that promote the enrichment of individuals, starting from embezzling other people's money in the world's largest banks, transferring the money of various organizations and firms to their own accounts and bankrupting them.

In order for each of us not to be deceived by these various conspiracies, we need to form a culture of information consumption in ourselves, strengthen our ideological immunity against various conspiracies, otherwise, at first glance, there may be no threat by getting into charming sites, advertisements, blogs, and frightening consequences may arise.

The task of information technology specialists is to put filters on malicious sites, advertisements and blogs at the level of providers, while other professionals will have to conduct various speeches, lectures, shows, and explanatory work based on their activities. It will also be necessary to publish books and brochures.

In conclusion, it can be observed that "today, in some parts of the world, as a result of such actions, great moral losses are taking place, the age-old values of the nation, national thinking and lifestyle are being lost, morals, family and community life, conscious way of life are in serious danger.

The worst thing is that the final result of such attacks is aimed at alienating a person from his native land and people, depriving him of patriotic feelings, and turning him into a person indifferent to everything," said I. Karimov in the work "High spirituality is an indomitable force" (12-13 -p.).

Therefore, the Internet is ignorance for the ignorant, crime for the criminal, adultery for the adulterer, usury for the usurer, theft for the thief, truth for the righteous, knowledge for the seeker of knowledge, loss for the scholar, oppression for the oppressor, invitation for the preacher, blessing for the lost, astrologer. is a source of prophecy for It's up to you, dear reader, to draw conclusions?

LITERATURE ANALYSIS. At the same time, the penetration of various destructive ideas aimed at capturing the hearts and minds of young people is becoming more visible, especially through the Internet. This process is also related to the increasing interest of our children in computer technologies and various computer games.

Propagators of destructive ideas are trying to use these interests effectively for their goals. In other words, the extremists, who are well aware that "gaming" is a threat to a certain part of society, are trying to occupy the minds of teenagers and young people in this way.

"Scientists I. P. Korolenko and T. A. Donskikh classified the signs of playfulness as follows:

1. An increase in the amount of time a teenager spends in the game
2. Previous habits and interests are narrowed and he thinks more about the game;
3. Being unable to leave the game even if he wins or loses;
4. Looking forward to the start of the game, getting restless when there is no game, nervousness;
5. The desire to play more and more, to go to the game more and more

6. Being unable to stop playing. "It's enough, I quit the game," he says, but when he sees his partners who played together before, when the game is discussed, he quickly changes his mind while passing by the playground;

7. Lying and stealing from parents to get money for gambling;

8. Lying and hiding his extreme playfulness from family members, doctors, etc., is a sign of a teenager's playfulness."

It can be seen that in most cases, a child can be lost as a result of not taking a serious approach to education during adolescence, and indifference to the child's behavior. As a result of the passion for Internet games, negative consequences such as stroke, ludomania, mental illnesses, and in most cases death due to a ruptured heart are visible. This is one of the biggest threats to our developing country. It is natural for a child to become more interested in forbidden things. A variety of computer games, such as "action", "strategy" or "shooter" games, regardless of which of them, can cause a child to have tantrums, aggression, It is important to learn how to use the Internet correctly to prevent mental disorders. As N. Kamilov noted: "The more ignorant a person is, the more he is prone to superstition, words

he is infatuated with magic, forms, and is so devoted to images and beliefs will be. And, on the contrary, as a person's enlightenment and knowledge increases, he...rises above sectarianism and fanaticism...".[1] Indulging in computer games has many negative effects on society. First of all, it is a moral damage, computer games are a moral corruption of our society immersing him in the swamp, equating a person with the happiness of self-realization. Islam In the teachings of our religion, such actions are strongly condemned: "After all, (did) A person who thinks that his bad work is beautiful (would he be like the one who found guidance)?!. Indeed, Allah chooses whomever He willsHe leads astray and guides whomever He wills. So, (O (Muhammad!) Don't let your soul die of sorrow for them. Of course, Allah knows what they do in secret." (Fatir, 8).

The behaviors of some young people tempted by Satan towards virtual games they look beautiful to themselves. A child who became a slave to games He is surprised by what he has done. There is a proverb in our people that says, "A person who is aware is not a fool!" "Spider There are more and more sites promoting fanaticism on the Internet. Such In this dangerous time, young people are advised to use only sites in the "Uz" domain will be done. After all, carelessly received information is a person it is clear that it will confuse. Religious needs from websites of different faiths and sects the people who are satisfied are in the hands of others, that is, the beneficiaries, through other sources let him not forget that he was not educated![2]

DISCUSSION. Computer games are stealing the time of young people. It is a worrying situation that young people are spending their time on idle games and getting to know complete strangers on social networks, while they are studying and gaining knowledge in Internet clubs. Because teenagers, who have become the age of internet and computer games, are completely disconnected from life, learning, professional learning and spiritual values, and become completely disillusioned. Nowadays, there are many hidden forces that are trying to influence teenagers negatively, inculcate their destructive ideas in their minds or lead them astray through computer games. Teenagers who indulge in computer games unknowingly become puppets of hidden forces.

Young people who are addicted to the computer spend all their time, even their sleep, with silly games. In the end, such disobedient youths reach the point of raising arms against their peers,

relatives and even their parents, if it is not an exaggeration. This leads to the spread of ignorance and ignorance in the society, and ultimately the country is in disarray.

Young people should not be deceived by such ideas, to the quagmire of error

We present the necessary recommendations to ensure that it does not sink. Our goal by driving young people to the Internet and spreading their destructive ideas like a virus is to warn the world about the true nature of criminals. A healthy mind

owners use internet facilities wisely to improve their knowledge.

But some young people are the cause of evil and moral decline in this network

"walking" on the sites where they will be, their own minds and those around them

it is clear that they are poisoning. That everyone gets what they need in the Internet market it is not appropriate to leave education to its own devices.

Therefore, it is necessary to develop the ability to analyze messages and information in young people. Because not every message is correct and impartial. About checking every piece of information, Allah the Exalted says: "O believers! If someone who is wicked brings you news, you should clarify (verify) the news so that you do not regret what you have done by causing suffering to a people without knowing (the true situation)!" (Hujurot, 6).

Internet addiction - a person cannot live without constantly being on social networks, without checking mail, loses contact with the real world, moves away from current problems, forgets, it occurs in unreliable, complex people and often in the younger generation. those who avoid personal communication and prefer virtual ones.

The role of the Internet in human life loses its meaning in this case, it exceeds the value of the gray and uninteresting ordinary world. In virtual reality, a person can create his own image, be different as he wants possible and this leads to internal balance. It is better to deal with changing real life and self-development than creating dreams.

Four stages of computer dependence: adaptation, habituation, influence on personal factors, as an integral part of human life. The emergence of the Internet and computer games. Virtual dating. Virtual games - impact on young people's thinking and outlook. Virtual world and manipulation.

Mental and physical dangers of computer games. Identity in the virtual world manifestation - "heroism". Violence, violence and brutality popular games: "Pubj", "Minecraft", "gta", "counter-strike", "Ever Quest", "Manhunt", Hilmiy Khidir Soriy "social communication through the Internet social survey on "impact on relations".[3]

Now there are special hospitals that treat internet addiction in many regions of the world, including European countries. We found it permissible to mention the events that took place in Korea and European countries as an example. It's a game of addiction; a person (child) begins to learn not life, but virtual life, and this is known to everyone that a person cannot be ready for any shock. Unfortunately, there are many people who have lost their lives because of this game. For example; In 2002, a 21-year-old American named Sean Willey shot himself in the forehead. It turned out that he went to the computer game called "EverQuest". It turned out that he lost in that game and could not bear to be separated from the points and awards he had collected, so he committed suicide. Unfortunately, these situations also happen in our country. Nowadays, the most popular game in Uzbekistan is PUBG, currently 60-70 percent of young people have personal accounts, and anyone without their protection system can hack into this system. And the result of this is not good. Half of the 12-16-year-olds who took part in a public survey in Uzbekistan often

prefer to chat with their peers and play computer games. 43.7 percent of teenagers limit themselves to reading educational literature. It is known that 1 out of 10 children does not read books other than educational literature. It was reported in the news that a 15-year-old boy stabbed his mother to death in Russia. We see that the mother told her to teach her child without playing a lot of computer games. We don't know when virtual games poisoned our minds.

CONCLUSION.

From a pedagogical point of view, the network has the following dangerous effects:

- being connected to the Internet network is one of the bad vices with negative effects of our time;

- to be lighthearted about studying and learning. Failure to independently complete lesson assignments at the expense of easily finding solutions to mathematical problems and ready-made lesson plans on the Internet;

- the risk of a negative impact on physical development, that is, the child has to sit in front of the monitor for a long time without active movement, etc.

In order to prevent these risks, it is necessary to pay attention to the following recommendations:

- do not leave your child unsupervised when he wants to use the network;
- inculcate in your child the habits of protection against the dangerous aspects listed above;
- explain that your child can find not only "good" but also "bad" information on the Internet from the first steps on the Internet;

- explain to your child the rules of registration when accessing the network, that is, it is impossible to give personal information;

- Explain the rules that need to be observed when saving a resource from the Internet;
- emphasize to your child that it is necessary not to forget the rules of discipline in the network as well as in real life;

- use "parental control" programs and set restrictions on your child's use of the Internet;

- make it a habit to monitor your child's communications every day;

- regularly develop your child's and your computer literacy;

- Share your knowledge. Remember that Internet security also depends on your knowledge and skills.

Therefore, the correct organization of the educational process, the continuous education of children control is very important. It is impossible to completely restrict the Internet to a child. The family is the first school in the upbringing of a perfect generation. The child from a young age not to lie, to think correctly, to be correct in everything teaching to use, forming feelings of love for the Motherland first in the family is done. We should not allow our children to control the Internet.

Therefore, what looks beautiful in the eyes of our children is external teaching to pay attention not to the side, but to the essence, to the patient of "playfulness". we are all equally responsible for protecting ourselves from exposure.

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